

Milestone MS3

Internal Cross-Cutting Workshop Nr. 1: Synchronising Work Packages' inputs/outputs

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MILESTONE

Milestone	MS3 Internal Cross-Cutting workshop: Synch WPs inputs/outputs (Nr.1)
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1. Means of verification

As stated in the Description of the Action, the means to verify that this milestone has been achieved is: "A report is available that defines the EOVs and ECVs to target across work packages WP3, WP4, and WP5 and defines the approach for setting requirements".

1.2. What is this milestone about?

Ocean indicators are a central, cross-cutting theme throughout ObsSea4Clim. In particular, Work Packages WP3 to WP5 (WP3-WP5) have identified several indicator-oriented tasks, all aimed at enhancing our ability to monitor, understand, measure, detect, predict, and project changes in the ocean (Fig. 1). These tasks focus on polar regions, the North Atlantic, and European regional seas, spanning timescales from extreme events to long-term shifts (Fig. 1). Establishing a collaborative foundation within ObsSea4Clim will help integrate these efforts, allowing for the development of co-constructed narratives that amplify the "voice of the ocean." By fully harnessing the upgraded capabilities provided through the project, ocean indicators will serve as an optimal tool to achieve these goals. This Milestone is dedicated to fostering cross-cutting collaboration within ObsSea4Clim, deeply embedded in the core activities of WP3-WP5, and is driven by two interactive workshops with project partners, particularly with experts from WP3, WP4 and WP5.

Particularly, this milestone is instrumental in developing coherent approaches for indicators, which will in turn help to provide robust recommendations to the essential variable framework and the ocean observing system. Also, it will ensure a collaborative framework across the WPs, allowing for the development of coherent approaches. This includes supporting advances on specific EOVs/ECVs and related ocean indicators for

improved ESM, and relevant uncertainty frameworks for specific agreed cross-cutting indicator themes. Also, this milestone is instrumental in creating an interoperable data ecosystem serving multidisciplinary needs while working together on coherent indicator approaches with underlying EOVs, and in agreed common regionalization testbeds. Also, this Milestone contributes to developing best practices and standards for the observing system. Also, the collaboration on agreed indicator themes will also be essential for developing relevant ocean narratives supporting the broader ocean and climate nexus. Two internal workshops were held online with Session 1 (held on 02.10.2024, 2-3:30 pm) and Session 2 (held on 17.10.2024, 2-3:30 pm). There was a broad engagement across ObsSea4Clim with more than 30 project experts actively contributing from all WPs, particularly for WP3-WP5.

Fig. 1: Left: Graphical view on the cross-cutting potential of ocean indicators in ObsSea4Clim, particularly for WP3, 4 and 5. Right: Overview of indicator themes, regionalization and timescales as integrated into the tasks of ObsSea4Clim for WP3-5.

a. 2.1 Alignment of ObsSea4Clim ocean indicators into the international dialogue building on the EOV/ECV framework

A foundation for the development of ocean indicators is the international framework of so-called Essential Variables. The Essential Ocean Variables' (EOVs) framework is a systematic approach implemented under the Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS)¹. The GOOS expert panels identify EOVs based on their significance for climate monitoring, operational ocean services, and ocean health. The selection process also considers the feasibility of observing or deriving these variables on a global scale, evaluating them through technical, political, and economic lenses. This ensures that chosen EOVs can be measured using proven, scientifically validated methods that are practical and sustainable for long-term global observation. The Global Climate Observing System (GCOS) under the World Meteorological Organization (WMO) has established the framework of Essential Climate Variables (ECVs)² covering atmospheric, oceanic and terrestrial domains, and the majority of EOVs are also ECVs (Bojinski and Richter, 2010). The Group on Earth Observations Biodiversity Observation Network has developed the framework of Essential Biodiversity Variables (EBVs) to advance the collection, sharing, and use of biodiversity information (Pereira et al. 2013; Navarro et al. 2017). ObsSea4Clim is deeply aligned with the concept of Essential Variables, which serves as its cross-cutting foundation, mainly guided through work done under WP2. Ocean indicators are based on Essential Variables, such as the Essential Ocean Variables, and indicators are derived from one or more of these variables. Hence, a tailored dialogue across ObsSea4Clim facilitated by ocean indicators will at the

¹ <https://goosocean.org/what-we-do/framework/essential-ocean-variables/>

² <https://gcos.wmo.int/en/essential-climate-variables>

same time allow for defining relevant Essential Variables, which in turn will contribute to the development of associated requirements.

Indicators are situated in an upper level of the so-called added value chain for ocean knowledge transfer and allow for an interlinkage between the three pillars of sustainable development, i.e., environment, society and economy (von Schuckmann et al., 2020). The international community has established a framework for global climate indicators under WMO GCOS³. The work in WP3 is particularly strongly aligned with this framework. The international ocean community is also currently working on the establishment of an international ocean indicator framework under GOOS⁴. These international standards on the definition of and criteria for ocean indicators should build the foundation across indicator-related work in ObsSea4Clim to ensure common understanding and methodologies. This milestone is aimed at building the foundation to build this mutual understanding with ObsSea4Clim.

b. 2.2 Work performed

The main approach for reaching this milestone relies on two interactive workshop sessions (online), which benefited from the broad engagement of all WPs, particularly for 3-5. The primary objectives of this workshop have been to:

- identify three cross-cutting indicator themes for proposition/demonstrator into the rolling review (see WP2; application: climate), agreed by all WPs: proposition by each WP & corresponding rationale;

³ <https://gcos.wmo.int/en/global-climate-indicators>

⁴ <https://goosocean.org/who-we-are/expert-panels/physics-and-climate-oopc/oopc-panel/oopc-activities/ocean-indicators/>

- establish a coherent approach for these 3 indicator themes, including methods, regionalization, EOV/ECV use, and uncertainty frameworks;
- develop a strategic framework for project-long collaboration on these three significant themes and across all WPs (e.g., for capacity exchange, new method developments, or new recommendations).

The outcome encompasses a mutual understanding of the meaning and criteria of ocean indicators (including the approach to EOV/ECV use). Also, the dialogue has resulted in an ObsSea4Clim co-constructed strategy for a specific set of indicators as a facilitator for cross-collaboration between WP3, WP4 & WP5 as described in this milestone.

i.2.2.1 Targeted joint action: Marine heatwaves and sea ice loss

To implement momentum on mutual exchange and cross-cutting collaboration, there is a need to identify common targets, to which each task can contribute within their respective work packages. There was a common agreement on targeting 2 specific indicator themes, which are tackled explicitly in all three WPs (Fig. 1, right). The first is referred to as marine heatwaves with a specific regional focus on the Mediterranean Sea, the Arctic Ocean and the Baltic Sea. Two areas of collaboration have been agreed:

1. Analyze and develop joint solutions for the temporal scalability of the marine heatwave indicator from the past (hindcast), the present (real-time), the near future (forecast) and the future (projection). This will encompass research and development for the connectivity between different systems, such as observations, Reanalyses, Forecasting tools and Earth System Models.
2. Analyze and enhance further our understanding of the drivers and interactions (e.g., impacts, long-term change) of MHWs, and their regionalization through a collaborative approach.

The second refers to the topic of sea ice loss. Two overarching collaboration goals have been agreed:

1. Jointly develop an indicator for sea ice loss, which is described by several EOVs/ECVs, and different methodologies. The aim is to propose an ObsSea4Clim standard methodology, including a recommendation for future improved and standardized monitoring of sea ice loss.
2. Analyze and develop joint solutions for the temporal scalability of the proposed indicator for sea ice loss (see 1.).

ii.2.2.2 Towards an internal framework for capacity dialogue and exchange

To pave the way for consistency of indicator-relevant advancements in ObsSea4Clim across the two agreed indicator themes (see section 1.1), mutual agreement has been reached to co-construct and develop an internal cross-cutting framework for capacity dialogue and exchange across 4 major areas of action (Fig. 2), i.e.

Fig. 2: Agreed areas of collaboration for the two ObsSea4Clim cross-cutting indicator themes, marine heatwaves and sea ice loss.

2. Project collaboration: there had been an overall agreement to engage in cross-cutting collaboration for the two indicator themes, for which particularly experts from WP3, WP4 and WP5 plan to contribute. For this purpose, 2 ad-hoc groups have been established (see Appendix 1 and 2).
3. A series of ad-hoc meetings have been agreed to foster collaborations for analysis developments and programme exchange.
4. There is a common agreement to foster collaboration for joint publications across ObsSea4Clim experts.
5. There had been discussions on organizing two potential hackathons for capacity developments and exchange, i.e. in the near term on marine heatwaves, and one at a later stage of the project for sea ice loss.

A central element of this collaboration could be a technical platform for exchanging programming codes (e.g., GitHub), which should be published by the respective developing experts with a specific DOI and open access under Zenodo, for example. All associated experts have agreed to jointly co-construct an improved methodology and tool for the monitoring of marine heatwaves and sea ice loss, which is planned to be made available to the broader community (e.g., scientific paper, published programming codes).

6. 3. Contribution to the ObsSea4Clim objectives

This milestone contributes to the achievement of the following specific objectives of the project.

#SO1	<p>To develop ocean indicators, provide improved EOV/ECVs and evolve European ocean observing</p>
<p>This milestone provides the direction and framework for the development of targeted ocean indicators and improved EOVs/ECVs in ObsSea4Clim. It will also ensure a collaborative framework across the WPs, allowing for the development of coherent approaches. It is also linked to the D3.2 that will come in later.</p>	
SO2	<p>To advance the use of EOV and ECV's for improved ESM and reduced uncertainty in projections</p>

<p>This Milestone does not directly contribute to the work with ESMs, as these efforts are concentrated in WP5), but it advances the work of ObsSea4Clim on specific EOVs/ECVs and related ocean indicators, and relevant uncertainty frameworks.</p>	
SO3	<p>To create an interoperable data ecosystem serving multidisciplinary needs</p>
<p>This milestone is linked to the D3.3 that will come in later. It defines areas where ocean indicators based on the EOV/ECV framework will be developed and tested.</p>	
SO4	<p>To develop best practices and standards for interoperable in-situ and satellite observing</p>
<p>This Milestone contributes to this SO by defining the ObsSea4Clim approach for the development of ocean indicators as part of the unifying and interoperable framework for ocean observing.</p>	
SO5	<p>To place Europe in the forefront of the global coordination of the broader ocean-climate nexus</p>
<p>This milestone is linked to the D3.1-D3.3 that will come in later.</p>	

7. 4. References

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8. Appendix 1: Ad-Hoc group on marine heatwaves

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10. Appendix 2: Ad-Hoc group on sea ice loss

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